

TODA YAMAMOTO CAUSALITY TEST BETWEEN CASHLESS ECONOMY AND ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

Chika Bright Ezekwu, Ph.D

Department of Economics, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt.

Email: ezekwuchika@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18373784>

Abstract

Cashless economy- a system where money transactions occur digitally is key to achieving sustained economic growth in Nigeria. The paper examined the impact of cashless economy on economic growth in Nigeria between 2010Q1 and 2024Q4. In this paper, the dependent variable is Per Capita Real Gross Domestic Product (PCRGDP) proxied for Economic Growth, and the explanatory variables are Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB), and Mobile Pay (MOP). The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics, Unit Root Test, and Toda Yamamoto modelling techniques. The results show that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not impact significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Point of sale Terminals (POS) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Point of sale Terminals (POS) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Web Pay (WEB) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Web Pay (WEB) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; and Mobile Pay (MOP) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Mobile Pay (MOP) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Mobile Pay (MOP) impacts significantly on economic growth in Nigeria while Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Web Pay (WEB) do not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria within the period of study. The study recommended amongst others that since POS and Mobile Pay have a significant positive impact on economic growth, the government and financial regulators should provide tax incentives, subsidies, or reduced transaction fees to merchants and consumers using POS and Mobile Pay and expand mobile network coverage and improve POS infrastructure, especially in rural and underserved areas. Also, monetary authorities should integrate POS and Mobile Pay into formal financial reporting to increase transparency and economic tracking.

Keywords: Cashless Economy, Economic Growth, Unit Root, Toda Yamamoto

Introduction

For any economy to develop, its mode of payment must be secured, affordable, and convenient (Nasamu et al. 2019). The introduction of electronic banking, online transactions and mobile banking in Nigeria has paved way for a new era of development where the use and demand for physical cash are gradually declining. This recent evolution of technology in the Nigerian financial institutions poses interesting questions for economic, financial institutions, business analyst and the government regarding the current economic status, logistics, and availability of instruments to guarantee economic growth and stability, efficiency and effectiveness of the cashless policy (Gbanador, 2023).

Since the inception of humanity, various payment methods have been used to purchase goods and service starting with trade by barter. The trade by barter method of transaction has been the foundation for the introduction of money and coins to solve the problem of double coincidence of wants and divisibility faced by trade by barter. The use of money/coins was introduced after the use of trade by barter method, and it has solved various challenges associated with trade by barter, but the use of money as an exchange medium has its own challenges and dis-advantages and can still be replaced with a better payment system- the cashless policy/banking (Nnanna & Dogo,2019).

Various advantages enjoyed by more developed nations such as the US has prompted the central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) to adopt the cashless policy. At the end of the 1980s the use of cash for purchasing consumption goods in the US has constantly dropped with inflation (Humphrey, 2004). Nigeria's aim to be among the biggest economy by 2020 had driven her to gradually move from a pure cash economy to a cashless policy. Since Nigeria gained her independence in 1960, there have been different constitutional reforms, change in economic and banking policies mainly aimed at stabilizing the economy, enhancing social welfare and enhancing economic growth and development (Uzowulu et al. 2024).

In view of being one the best and biggest economies 2020, the CBN has started implementing the cashless policy/banking in some major states/cities in Nigeria such as Lagos, Kano Port-Harcourt and Onitsha. The CBN and Proc cashless policy activities have asserted reduction in crime rates, minimized risk associated with carrying huge sums of money reduction in political corruption, reduction in banking cost, improvement on monetary policy in management of inflation and the overall growth and development of the economy of Nigeria as a advantages associated with the implementation of the cashless policy (Enefiok&Emenyi, 2024).

Literature Review

This section covers conceptual clarification, theoretical review and empirical literature review.

Cashless Economy

The concept of cashless economy has been defined in a variety of ways by various scholars. Kenyangi (2024) defined cashless economy as an economic system where transactions are conducted electronically, eliminating the need for physical cash. It consists of digital transactions, a robust electronic payment infrastructure, financial inclusion, a regulatory framework, and interoperability. The benefits according to Kenyangi include reduced costs, increased efficiency, enhanced security, traceability, increased access, empowerment, economic growth, convenience, and innovative services

Web-based Transactions

Web-based transactions refer to the process of conduction financial transactions, such as payments and transfers, through interest-based platforms. According to Uzochukwu and Okoli (2016), with the increasing penetration of internet services and the steady growth of e-commerce, web-based transactions have become an important avenue for individuals and businesses to engage in various financial activities conveniently and securely.

Point of sale (POS) Transactions

Point of sale (POS) transactions refers to the process of conducting financial transactions using a point-of-sale terminal, typically through debit or credit cards. This method of payment has gained popularity in recent years due to its convenience, speed, and security as suggested by Uzochukwu and Okoli (2016). As noted by Nnanna & Dogo (2019), customers no longer need to carry large amounts of cash and can easily make secure payments using their cards.

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) Transactions

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transactions refer to the process of conducting financial transactions using an ATM, which allows individuals to withdraw cash, deposits funds, check balances, transfer money between accounts, pay utility bills, and perform other banking activities without needing to visit a physical bank branch (Nnenna & Dogo, 2019). As noted by Nwachukwu, Okeke & Udeh (2020), customers can access their bank accounts 24/7 and perform various transactions at their own convenience, eliminating the need to visit a physical bank during working hours. This accessibility has significantly improved customer satisfaction and banking efficiency in Nigeria.

Mobile Banking

This is an electronic payment system that allows the banks to consummate financial transactions via a mobile phone. According to Gbanador (2023), mobile banking is performed using a smartphone or similar device software.

Economic Growth

According to Kuznets (1971), a country's economic growth is a long-term rise in the capacity of supply leading to increase in the production of goods and services for the population accompanied by advancing technology and the institutional and ideological adjustment that it demands.

Economic growth refers to a positive change in the level of production of goods and services produced by a country over a period of time. When measured over the population of goods and services in a given year is divided by the population of the country within the given period (Ogbulu, 2009). To Akpakpan (1987), economic growth is the achievement of yearly increase in both the total and per capital output of goods and services. It refers to the sustained increase in the actual output of goods and services of the nation concerned.

Theoretical Literature

This paper is anchored on Rogers (1962) Diffusion of Innovation Theory and The Solow and Swan (1956) Theory of Economic Growth.

Diffusion of Innovation Theory

According to Rogers (1962), this theory explains how innovations, such as cashless payment systems, are adopted by individuals and organizations. It suggest that adoption follows a pattern, with categories of people including innovators, early adopters, early majority, late majority and laggards. The theory identifies key factors influencing adoption, such as perceived benefits, compatibility with existing

systems, simplicity, trialability, and observable results. This theory explains how new ideas and technologies, like cashless payments, spread through a society. It outlines the stages individuals go through from learning about an innovation (knowledge) to forming an opinion (persuasion), deciding to adopt it (decision) and finally using and confirming its benefits (implementations and confirmation).

The Solow-Swan Theory of Economic Growth

The Solow-Swan model is a neoclassical growth theory developed independently by Robert Solow and Trevor Swan in 1956, explaining long term economic growth through capital accumulation, labour growth and technological progress. It posits that capital accumulate drives short-term growth, but diminishing returns lead to a steady state where growth depends on exogenous technological advancements. The model highlights how technology is a boundless, yet external factor essential for sustained increase in per capital output.

The key components of the Solow-Swan Model include

- i. Capital Accumulation: The model emphasizes how savings and investment in new capital (like machinery and buildings) increase a nation's productive capacity, driving short-term growth.
- ii. Labour growth: The growth of the population (labour force) is another factor, contributing to overall economic output.
- iii. Technological progress: According to Solow and Swan, this is the crucial element for long-term growth, as it increases productivity without requiring more capital or labour inputs.

The Solow-Swan model provided a robust framework for understanding long-run economic growth, building on earlier Keynesian models. It highlights that while capital accumulation is vital for short-term growth, technological advancement is the key to sustained increases in the long-run.

Empirical Literature

Enefiok & Emenyi (2024) studied cashless policy and economic growth in Nigeria. Specifically, the study aimed at ascertaining the relationship between web-based transactions, POS transactions and ATM transactions with real GDP of Nigeria over a period of 10 years (2013-2022). The findings revealed that POS transactions and ATM transactions have an insignificant positive relationship with real GDP while web-based transactions showed an insignificant inverse relationship.

Mbabie, Aigbedion & Obumneke (2024) studied the impact of cashless policy intensity on economic growth in Nigeria from 2009 to 2022. The Fully Modified Ordinary Least Squares (FMOLS) methods was employed. The results show that there is ATM transaction intensity negative impact on economic growth in Nigeria. The results further showed that the internet transaction intensity has a positive but insignificant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Sreenu (2020) studied cashless payment policy and its effects on economic growth of India: an expository study from 2010 to 2018. The study employed the panel vector error correction model, Padroni residual cointegration and the hypothetical prototypical method. The results show that customers and sellers accept a cashless system policy. In the short period, the result show a causality model running from a cad

system to a check payment and telegraphic transfer system, and a causality model running from a telegraphic payment system to a card payment system. In the long run, the result show a positive outcome in using a cashless policy on Indian economy.

Ibe, & Odi (2018) studied cashless policy in models of economic growth: the Nigerian evidence from 2009 to 2016. The variables used for the study were Gross Domestic Product (GDP) as the dependent variable while Automated Teller Machine (ATM), mobile banking (MOBK) and Point of Sale (POS) were the independent variables. The findings of the study show the existence of a long run significant relationship between the variables of cashless policy and economic growth in Nigeria. The result further show that the ATM seems to be the best and most common based on the Magnitude of its relationship with GDP.

El-Yaqub (2024) carried out a study on analysis of the impact of cashless policy and naira redesign on economic growth in Nigeria: The study employed quantitative data analysis to establish the correlation between Nigeria's cashless policy and economic growth. The findings indicate the presence of a causal association between the cashless policy and economic growth in Nigeria.

Nasamu, Danjuma & Ozah (2020) studied the effect of cashless policy on Nigeria's economic growth from 2011 to 2018. Multiple regressions were applied to determine the impact of the policy on the GDP using the ATM, POS and the WEB. The study revealed that ATM has a positive effect on GDP. On the other hand, the regression results also show that POS and WEB had a negative effect on GDP.

Gbanador (2023) studied the effect of cashless policy on economic growth in Nigeria: an autoregressive distributed Lag (ARDL) was used for the data analysis. The findings revealed a significant relationship between cheque (CQ) and internet banking (IB) with the Gross Domestic Product while the relationship between the Automated Teller machine and the Gross Domestic Product is negatively insignificant.

Uzowulu, Anyanwu & Amakor (2024) studied the impact of cashless policy on the Nigerian economy from 2009 to 2022. The time series data of the variables, ATM transactions, POS transactions, mobile banking transactions, Web pay transactions and Nominal GDP were obtained from CBN statistical bulletin (2021). The study employed multiple linear regression model and the Granger Causality Test. The Findings of the study showed that, the value of ATM transactions is positively related to economic growth but has not significantly impact economic growth in Nigeria and that of POS transactions is negatively related to and has significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria.

Okereke (2016) examined the impact of Automated Teller Machine (ATM) transaction value, point of sale terminal, internet banking and mobile banking transactions value on economic value of Nigeria. The quantitative design was used and Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method of multiple regression analysis was employed to test the research hypothesis. The findings of the study show that only point of sales terminal was significant to economic growth while Automated Teller Machine, mobile banking and internet banking are insignificant to economic growth within the period of study.

Suberu, Afonja, Akande & Olure Bank (2015) studied the implication of cashless policy on the banking sector with a view of revealing the possible challenges and prospects to the Nigerian economy. The

ordinary Least Squares econometric technique was employed to analyze the data collected. The findings of the study revealed that the marginal productivity coefficient of bank credit to the domestic economy is positive but insignificant.

Research Methodology

The paper adopted the ex-post facto research design. The choice of ex-post facto research design was informed by the fact the numerical data required for the actual empirical analysis was collected from secondary sources.

Model Specification

This study adopted and modified the linear model of Nasamu, Danjuma & Ozah (2019), whose work focused on effect of cashless policy on Nigeria’s Economic Growth from 2011 to 2018. The multiple regression model is specified below:

$$GDP = \delta + B_1ATM + B_2POST + B_3WFB + \delta \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where;

- GDP: = Gross Domestic product
- ATM: = Automated Teller machine
- POS = Point of sale
- WEB = Internet banking
- δ = Constant
- B₁-B₃ = coefficients of independent variables
- E = error term

However, the adopted model was modified to enable us include the variables of the present study. The functional form of the model to be used in this study is expressed as:

$$PCRGDP = f(ATM, POS, WEB, MOB) \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

The mathematical form of the model is stated:

$$PCRGDP = B_0 + B_1ATM + B_2POS + B_3WEB + BOB \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

The Econometric form of the model is stated:

$$PCRGDP = B_0 + B_1ATM + B_2POS + B_3WEB + B_4MOB + \mu \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Where:

PCRDGP = Per Capital Real Gross Domestic Product a proxy for Economic Growth.

ATM = Automated Teller Machine Transactions

POS = Point of Sale Transactions

WEB = Internet Banking Transactions

MOB = Mobile Banking Transactions

F = Functionality Symbol

B₀ = The regression constant

B₁ to B₄ = The parameter estimates of the explanatory variables

U = Error term

All other variables are as earlier defined.

A priori theoretical expectations.

Based on economic theory, we expect the following signs of the parameter estimates

$B_1 > 0$; $B_2 > 0$; $B_3 > 0$; and $B_4 > 0$

The implication of the above sizes of the coefficients of the explanation, variables shows that we expect a positive relationship between automated teller machine, point of sale, internet banking and mobile banking and per capital real gross domestic product.

Estimation Techniques

This study examined the effects of cashless economy on economic growth in Nigeria using Toda Yamamoto modelling technique to analyze the data. The research covers 43 years, from 2010Q1 to 2024Q4. To determine if each variable is stationary, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test for stationarity was used. The World Bank World Development Indicators provided the annual time series data used in this analysis for the years 2010Q1–2024Q4.

Results and Discussion

For this paper, the empirical data was analyzed in stages. Initially, the data is analyzed using descriptive statistics. Next, the unit root test is executed. Finally, Toda-Yamamoto modelling technique was used to complete the inquiry.

Descriptive statistics

The descriptive statistics summary for the variables used in this investigation is shown in Table 1 below. It displays the mean, median, maximum, minimum, and standard deviation, among other data.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	PCRGDP	ATM	POS	WEB	MOP
Mean	347509.6	12207.35	143828.2	321953.6	50671.89
Median	344169.7	6453.528	1774.799	368.8416	1429.094
Maximum	421427.3	36863.85	1908613.	1938611.	303043.5
Minimum	327720.3	399.7100	12.72000	25.05000	6.650000
Std. Dev.	15751.28	11595.83	408812.8	501767.7	87683.49
Skewness	2.308849	0.779100	3.117865	1.445527	1.589407
Kurtosis	10.45184	1.968358	11.71535	4.113710	4.028448
Jarque-Bera	192.1326	8.730680	287.1042	23.99636	27.90641
Probability	0.000000	0.012710	0.000000	0.000006	0.000001
Sum	20850577	732440.9	8629694.	19317216	3040314.
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.46E+10	7.93E+09	9.86E+12	1.49E+13	4.54E+11
Observations	60	60	60	60	60

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

According to Table 1, the mean value of Economic Growth (PCRGDP) is 347509.6, with a standard deviation of 15751.28. The long-left tail of Economic Growth (PCRGDP) is indicated by its positive skewness score (2.308849). Furthermore, the Economic Growth (PCRGDP) kurtosis value of 10.45184 (greater than 3) suggests that it is leptokurtic. When the values go higher than the sample mean, this implies a peak distribution.

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has a mean of 12207.35, and its standard deviation is 11595.83. Additionally, the Automated Teller Machine (ATM) has a long-right tail, as indicated by its positive skewness score of 0.779100. The kurtosis value of 1.968358 (less than 3) shows that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) is also leptokurtic, having a peak distribution where values are higher than the sample mean.

The standard deviation is 408812.8 and the mean for the Point of sale Terminals (POS) is 143828.2. The Point of sale Terminals (POS) long-left tail is indicated by its positive skewness score of 3.117865. As evidenced by its kurtosis score of 11.71535 (more than 3), the Point of sale Terminals (POS) is similarly leptokurtic, having a peak distribution when values exceed the sample mean.

The standard deviation is 501767.7 and the Web Pay (WEB) mean is 321953.6. A platykurtic distribution is suggested by the Web Pay (WEB) kurtosis of 4.113710, which is greater than 3, despite its positive skewness of 1.445527, which indicates a long-left tail. With values that primarily fall below the sample mean, this points to a somewhat peaked distribution.

The mean and standard deviation of the Mobile Pay (MOP) are 50671.89 and 87683.49, respectively. The Mobile Pay (MOP) shows a mesokurtic distribution with a kurtosis of 4.028448, or higher than 3, and a positive skewness of 1.589407, which indicates a long right tail. The values appear to have a normal distribution since they are clustered around the mean.

The variables' Jarque-Bera statistics are a key component of this table. The values of Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of Sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB), and Mobile Pay (MOP) are higher than 5.99, suggesting that these variables are not normally distributed.

Given these findings, it is crucial to test for the stationarity and long-term correlations of the variables, as utilising the variables at their level may lead to false conclusions. The study uses the Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) technique to do a unit root test to make sure the variables are stable.

Unit Root Test

Tables 2 and 3 below present's results of stationarity test for each of variables used using Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and KPSS tests.

Table 2: Unit Root Test Results

Variables	Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test				
	Level	1 st Difference	2 nd Difference	Status	Remarks
PCRGDP	-0.539186	-0.285369	-7.526892	I(2)	Stationary

ATM	0.603100	-2.043907	-6.683457	I(2)	Stationary
POS	6.204972	-0.311609	-7.554990	I(2)	Stationary
WEB	2.166380	0.169204	-6.248605	I(2)	Stationary
MOP	-0.421353	-4.639602	-	I(1)	Stationary
Critical Values	Level	1 st Difference	2 nd Difference		
1%	-3.548208	-3.548208	-3.550396		
5%	-2.912631	-2.912631	-2.913549		
10%	-2.594027	-2.594027	-2.594521		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

Table 3: KPSS Root Test Results

Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) Test					
Variables	Level	1 st Difference	2 nd Difference	Status	Remarks
PCRGDP	0.132361	-	-	I(0)	Stationary
ATM	0.854150	0.342280	-	I(1)	Stationary
POS	0.496208	0.508133	0.239629	I(2)	Stationary
WEB	0.762110	0.893773	0.179685	I(2)	Stationary
MOP	0.673424	0.797204	0.070758	I(2)	Stationary
Critical Values	Level	1 st Difference	2 nd Difference		
1%	0.739000	0.739000	0.739000		
5%	0.463000	0.463000	0.463000		
10%	0.347000	0.347000	0.347000		

Source: Author’s Computation (2025)

The outcomes of unit root test in Table 2 using ADF, revealed that Mobile Pay (MOP) was stationary at levels, i.e. 1(1), while Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Web Pay (WEB) were stationary at second difference, i.e. 1(2). Hence, this study concludes that the variables used in the model using ADF were integrated of different order integration, that is, 1(1) and 1(2).

The result of the KPSS presented in Table 3 revealed that Economic Growth (PCRGDP) was stationary at levels, i.e. 1(0); Automated Teller Machine (ATM) was stationary at first difference, i.e. 1(1) while Point of Sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB) and Mobile Pay (MOP) were stationary at second difference, i.e. 1(2). Hence, this study concludes that the variables used in the model using KPSS were integrated of different order integration, that is, 1(0), 1(1) and 1(2).

Since the ADF results indicate that the series are of the different order of integration, we proceed to conduct co-integration and then the Toda Yamamoto modeling technique.

Lag Order Selection

An important preliminary step in model building and estimating the Toda Yamamoto model is the selection of the lag order. In this study we used some commonly used lag-order selection criteria to choose the lag order, such as the "Akaike information criterion (AIC)", "Schwartz criterion (SC)", "Hannan-Quinn criterion (HQC)" and "final prediction error (FPE)" to determine the optimum lag and then analyze the residuals.

Table 4: Optimum Lag Test

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria
Endogenous variables: LOG(PCRGDP) LOG(ATM) LOG(POS) LOG(WEB)
LOG(MOP)
Exogenous variables: C
Date: 11/22/25 Time: 09:36
Sample: 2010Q1 2024Q4
Included observations: 56

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-132.6260	NA	9.38e-05	4.915215	5.096050	4.985324
1	309.6714	789.8169	3.17e-11	-9.988266	-8.903256	-9.567610
2	355.9750	74.41642*	1.52e-11*	-10.74911*	-8.759922*	-9.977904*
3	366.8572	15.54599	2.65e-11	-10.24490	-7.351540	-9.123150
4	394.2337	34.22060	2.72e-11	-10.32977	-6.532240	-8.857478

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

Table 4 shows that lag 2 is chosen as the optimum lag in the specification of Toda Yamamoto model on the relationship between the variables in this study for the period between 2010Q1 and 2024Q4. Thus, we now estimate and analyze the Toda Yamamoto model.

Toda Yamamoto Estimation Results for the Model

The result of the Toda Yamamoto estimation is presented in table 5 below.

Table 5: Toda Yamamoto Causality Test Results

VAR Granger Causality/Block Exogeneity Wald Tests

Date: 11/22/25 Time: 09:38

Sample: 2010Q1 2024Q4

Included observations: 54

Dependent variable: LOG(PCRGDP)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
LOG(ATM)	4.407402	2	0.1104
LOG(POS)	7.573355	2	0.0227
LOG(WEB)	1.844770	2	0.3976
LOG(MOP)	7.393136	2	0.0248
All	15.77402	8	0.0457

Dependent variable: LOG(ATM)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
LOG(PCRGD P)	1.790093	2	0.4086
LOG(POS)	2.193873	2	0.3339
LOG(WEB)	0.713615	2	0.6999
LOG(MOP)	2.576899	2	0.2757
All	5.307858	8	0.7242

Dependent variable: LOG(POS)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
LOG(PCRGD P)	14.03367	2	0.0009
LOG(ATM)	3.030155	2	0.2198
LOG(WEB)	2.143328	2	0.3424
LOG(MOP)	11.31620	2	0.0035
All	15.38869	8	0.0520

Dependent variable: LOG(WEB)

Excluded	Chi-sq	df	Prob.
LOG(PCRGD P)	3.079693	2	0.2144
LOG(ATM)	11.22239	2	0.0037
LOG(POS)	2.896868	2	0.2349
LOG(MOP)	4.072415	2	0.1305
All	18.64752	8	0.0169

Dependent variable: LOG(MOP)

Excluded	Chi-sq	Df	Prob.
LOG(PCRGD P)	1.207546	2	0.5467
LOG(ATM)	1.956252	2	0.3760
LOG(POS)	1.218364	2	0.5438
LOG(WEB)	3.270315	2	0.1949
All	6.547485	8	0.5861

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

The study shows that jointly there is a causality running from Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB), and Mobile Pay (MOP) to Economic Growth (PCRGDP) but individually with exception of Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Mobile Pay (MOP) that have a causal effect on Economic Growth (PCRGDP); Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Web Pay (WEB) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth (PCRGDP) in Nigeria within the period of study.

Also, when Automated Teller Machine (ATM) is the dependent variable, the study shows that both jointly and individually there is no causality running from Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Point of sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB) and Mobile Pay (MOP) to Automated Teller Machine (ATM) in Nigeria.

Furthermore, when Point of sale Terminals (POS) is the dependent variable, the study shows that jointly there is a causality running from Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Web Pay (WEB) and Mobile Pay (MOP) to Point of sale Terminals (POS) but individually with exception of Economic Growth (PCRGDP) and Mobile Pay (MOP) all the other variables (Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Web Pay (WEB)) do not have a causal effect on Point of sale Terminals (POS) in Nigeria.

When Web Pay (WEB) is the dependent variable, the study shows that jointly there is no causality running from Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Mobile Pay (MOP) to Web Pay (WEB) but individually with exception of Automated Teller Machine (ATM),

all the other variables has no causality running from Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Mobile Pay (MOP) to Web Pay (WEB) in Nigeria.

Also, When Mobile Pay (MOP) is the dependent variable, the study shows that both jointly and individually there is no causality running from Economic Growth (PCRGDP), Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Web Pay (WEB) to Mobile Pay (MOP) in Nigeria.

Diagnostic Testing Results for the Model

Table 6 below displays the findings from the diagnostic or post-estimation testing. The results of the VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests are displayed in Table 4.5. The study comes to the conclusion that the model passes the full post estimation test, as shown in Table 4.5.

Table 6: Diagnostic Test Results for the Model

VAR Residual Serial Correlation LM Tests

Null Hypothesis: no serial correlation at lag order h

Date: 11/22/25 Time: 09:39

Sample: 2010Q1 2024Q4

Included observations: 54

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob
1	3.452204	0.4861
2	20.58329	0.7156
3	16.15321	0.9102

Probs from chi-square with 25 df.

Source: Author's Computation (2025)

Discussion of Findings

Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Economic Growth (PCRGDP) in Nigeria

From the results of the Toda and Yamamoto causality test the study revealed that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not has a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This is shown by the chi-sq value of 4.407402 and probability value of 0.1104 which is less than the 0.05 percent. This implies that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. In Nigeria, major cities like Lagos and Abuja have thousands of ATMs, and people can easily access cash for daily transactions. However, despite this high ATM density, these cities still face challenges like: low manufacturing output, High unemployment rates and Infrastructure deficits (roads, electricity, etc.) This shows that even though people can withdraw money conveniently, it doesn't automatically translate into more goods being produced, more investments being made, or faster economic growth. The ATMs are just tools for cash access-they don't generate economic activity on their own. So, the causal effect is missing because ATMs don't directly influence the core factors that drive

Nigeria's GDP growth. This finding agrees with the works of Igoni, Onwumere, & Ogiri (2020) and Gbanador (2023). These studies found no causal significant impact of ATM (among other digital finance channels) on Nigeria's GDP.

4.4.2 Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Economic Growth (PCRGDP) in Nigeria

The study revealed that Point of sale Terminals (POS) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This is shown by the chi-sq value of 7.573355 and probability value of 0.0227 which is greater than the 0.05 percent. This implies that Point of sale Terminals (POS) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This suggest that POS terminals increase financial transactions and formalize the economy, which directly stimulates business activity and economic growth. When people and businesses use POS terminals, money moves faster through the formal banking system. This reduces cash hoarding, improves tax collection, and increases transparency in business transactions. As a result, businesses can expand, investments are easier to track, and economic activity grows, which contributes directly to Nigeria's GDP. This finding agrees with the works of Afaha (2019), Adesete, Mohammed & Risikat (2021), Anifowose & Ekperiware (2022), and Adeniji (2025). These studies shows that digital payment systems including POS have a positive influence on Nigeria's GDP.

Web Pay (WEB) and Economic Growth (PCRGDP) in Nigeria

The results of the Toda and Yamamoto causality test revealed that Web Pay (WEB) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This is shown by the chi-sq value of 1.844770 and probability value of 0.3976 which is less than the 0.05 percent. This implies that Web Pay (WEB) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. Web Pay (WEB) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria because Web Pay adoption in Nigeria is still low, so it does not significantly influence overall economic activity. While Web Pay enables online payments, only a small fraction of businesses and consumers use it regularly due to limited internet access, low digital literacy, and trust issues. Because of this low usage, the volume of transactions through Web Pay is too small to meaningfully impact GDP or economic growth. This finding agrees with the works of Zaccheus (2023), Adebisi, Zannu & Dada (2023), and Osakwe & Akunna (2023). These studies found out that Web Pay transactions have a negative but not statistically significant effect on household consumption expenditure. Also, they found out that web pay channels have an insignificant effect on Nigeria's GDP.

Mobile Pay (MOP) and Economic Growth (PCRGDP) in Nigeria

The results of the Toda-Yamamoto causality test used in this study revealed that Mobile Pay (MOP) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This is shown by the chi-sq value of 7.393136 and probability value of 0.0248 which is less than the 0.05 percent. This implies that Mobile Pay (MOP) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria within period of study. This suggests that Mobile Pay (MOP) increases financial inclusion, enabling more people and small businesses to participate

in the formal economy, which directly stimulates economic activity. Mobile Pay allows individuals in rural and underserved areas to send, receive, and store money without needing a traditional bank account. This expands access to financial services, encourages transactions, savings, and investments, and reduces reliance on cash. As more people and businesses transact digitally, economic activity is tracked, efficient, and contributes directly to GDP growth, creating a causal effect. This finding agrees with the works of Mohammed (2019), Asongu & Odhiambo (2022), and Orekoya (2022).

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of cashless economy on economic growth in Nigeria between 2010Q1 and 2024Q4. In this study, the dependent variable was Economic Growth (PCRGDP), and the explanatory variables were Automated Teller Machine (ATM), Point of sale Terminals (POS), Web Pay (WEB), and Mobile Pay (MOP). The data was analysed using descriptive statistics, Unit Root Test, and Toda Yamamoto modelling technique. The study found that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Automated Teller Machine (ATM) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Point of sale Terminals (POS) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Point of sale Terminals (POS) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; Web Pay (WEB) do not have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Web Pay (WEB) do not impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria; and Mobile Pay (MOP) have a causal effect on Economic Growth in Nigeria, meaning that Mobile Pay (MOP) impacts significantly on Economic Growth in Nigeria. The study therefore concludes that Point of sale Terminals (POS) and Mobile Pay (MOP) impacts significantly on economic growth in Nigeria while Automated Teller Machine (ATM) and Web Pay (WEB) do not have a significant effect on economic growth in Nigeria within the period of study.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Instead of only installing more ATMs, the government and banks could implement policies that ensure people especially small businesses and entrepreneurs can access loans, savings accounts, and digital payment systems. This would help turn the convenience of ATMs into actual economic activity, such as starting businesses, expanding production, or investing in skills, which directly drives economic growth.
2. The government and financial institutions can provide tax breaks, subsidies, or training programs to encourage SMEs to adopt POS technology. By increasing the use of POS, more transactions enter the formal economy, improving financial inclusion, transparency, and ultimately driving economic growth.
3. To Promote widespread adoption of Web Pay through digital literacy programs and incentives for online businesses, the government, banks, and fintech companies can collaborate to: Educate businesses and consumers about using Web Pay securely, offer incentives, like reduced transaction fees or tax benefits, for businesses that adopt online payments. This would increase the usage of Web Pay, integrate

more transactions into the formal economy, and potentially allow it to have a positive causal effect on economic growth over time.

4. To encourage and expand Mobile Pay adoption through supportive regulation and infrastructure development, the government and financial regulators can partner with telecom companies to expand mobile network coverage, especially in rural areas, provide regulatory frameworks that ensure secure, low-cost Mobile Pay transactions, offer incentives for businesses and consumers to adopt Mobile Pay. This would increase financial inclusion, stimulate more formal economic transactions, and strengthen Mobile Pay's positive causal impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

References

Adebisi, A. O., & Zannu, S. M., & Dada, J. O. (2023). Effect of Digital Payment on Sustainable Growth in Nigeria. *FUOYE Journal of Finance & Contemporary Issues*, 5(1), 76-90.

Adeniji, K. A. (2025). Digital Payment System and Economic Growth in Nigeria: A Longitudinal Study (2012 – 2024). *Faculty of Natural and Applied Sciences Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Computing*, 2(2), 52–57.

Adesete, A., Mohammed, A. A., & Risikat, O. (2021). Financial Innovation and Economic Growth: Empirical Evidence from Nigeria. *Euro Economica*.

Afaha, J. S. (2019). Electronic Payment Systems (E-payments) and Nigeria Economic Growth. *European Business & Management*, 5(6), 68–78.

Anifowose, T., & Ekperiware, M. (2022). The effect of automated teller machines, point of sale terminals and online banking transactions on economic growth in Nigeria. *Open Access Research Journal of Science and Technology*, 4(2), 16-33. <https://doi.org/10.53022/oarjst.2022.4.2.0024>

Asongu, S. A., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2022). The Role of Economic Growth in Modulating Mobile Money Drivers in Developing Countries.

Daniel, D.G., R.W. Swartz, and A.L. Fermar, (2004)" – Economics of a cashless society: An Analysis of costs and Benefits of payment instruments, AEL-Brookings Joint Center.

Gbanador, M. A. (2023). The Effect of Cashless Policy on Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Autoregressive Distributed Lag Approach. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 23(6), 22–31.

- Humphrey, D.B (2004): - Replacement of cash by cards in U.S consumer payments, *Journal of Economics and Business*, 56, 211 -225
- Humphrey, D.B. & A.N. Berger (1990). *Market failure and Resource use: Economics incentives to use different payment instruments*. New York, Monograph Series in Finance and Economics
- Igoni, S., Onwumere, J. U. J., & Ogiri, I. H. (2020). The Nigerian Digital Finance Environment and Its Economic Growth: Pain or Gain. *Asian Journal of Economics, Finance and Management*, 2(2), 1-10.
- Kenyangi, O.F. (2024). The evolution of cashless economy in Nigeria: policies, impacts, and future directions. *Research Invention Journal of Law, Communication and Languages*, 3 (3):97-102
- Mohammed, A. M. (2019). Exploring the Relationship between Mobile Money Development and Economic Growth: Evidence from Nigeria. Master's thesis, University of Cape Town.
- Nasamu, G., Danjuma, T. U. & Ozah, J.P. (2019). Effect of cashless policy on Nigeria's economic growth. *Malete Journal of Accounting and Finance*, 1(1)
- Orekoya, S. (2022). Macroeconomic Effects of Mobile Money in Nigeria." *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 64(2), 22-45.
- Osakwe, C. I., & Akunna, R. C. (2023). Effect of Internet Banking on Growth of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. *Journal of the Management Sciences*, 60(1), 45-60.
- Zaccheaus, J. (2023). Effect of Electronic Payment System on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *London Journal of Research in Management & Business*, 23(7), 39-51.